

Spectroscopic study of photo-physical parameters of dyes in different solvents environment

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Abstract:

Surrounding condition has a great role on the spectral characteristics of photosensitive dyes. Solvents having different characteristic and influence in the change of both ground and excited state of photo sensitive dyes as solvent molecules interact with the probe molecule in different way in its microenvironment [1-5]. Photo chemical and photo physical phenomenon are applied in our everyday life like paints, highway hoardings, light fastness in dyeing fiber and in determining the surfactant characteristics etc. Low energy ground state and high energy excited state electronic transition is the cause of spectroscopic transition. The characteristics of spectroscopic transitions also affected by the free energy changes or interaction among dye and solvents [6-12] molecules. Surface mole fraction of solvents around probe molecules differ from the bulk causes change in spectroscopic properties in mixture of different solvents. Different electronic state arises due to difference of density of electrons [13-18] in surrounding microenvironment of solvent. On the other hand the fluorescence emission spectra of many fluorophores are too much sensitive to the solvent polarity which also responsible for bathochromic spectral shift towards higher wavelength and hypsochromic shifts towards lower wavelength. In general, better stability of dye molecules in the higher energy state due to enhance polar [19] characteristic in compare to the lower energy state and with increase in solvent polarity indicating lowering the energy of transition through red shift. This work presents solvent effect studies with a number of photo sensitive dyes [11,12] in microenvironment of aprotic and protic medium. From various interaction parameter studies and analysis, it has been found that at excited state dye interact with micro environment either through special intermolecular hydrogen bonding or polar-polar interaction [20-22] with media in case of every dyes.

Keywords: Solvent; Dye; Interaction; Emission; Absorbance

1. Introduction:

The photo sensitive dyes show characteristics spectral nature and those spectral natures are too much dependent on surrounding environment [23]. The application in X-ray, advertisement hoardings, as optical brightness in television screen are the effect the photo physical and photochemical phenomena. Those phenomena also use to detect the cracks in metals, concrete, also in solute solvent interaction in surfactant effect as well as in molecular course of drug application. So, solvent media and micro-heterogeneous environment like oil in water (micelle), water in oil (reverse micelle) have direct effect on the spectroscopy of photo sensitive dye. The jumping of electron from equilibrium ground state to non-equilibrium excited state is the cause of spectroscopic transition. The free energy change due to solvent solute interaction also depends on solvation. Solvent causes stabilization of electronic energy levels [24] and effect on the photo physical properties. As example in mixture of solvents environment the local mole fraction of solvent surrounding the solute molecule at surface zone are differ from the same in the bulk zone. The spectroscopic nature of probe

molecule changes in mixed solvent

environment due to different type of interaction caused by the electronic state which varies with different electron density. It causes on the shifting of the spectra to higher or lower wavelength. The polar characteristic of solvent or micro environment surrounded to the dye molecule also responsible for the change in absorption and emission spectra. The λ_{Max} may shift either to higher wave length (red or bathochromic shift) or to the lower wave length (blue or hypsochromic) with change in the polarity of solvent. Analyzing of shift we can explain the nature of the interaction among dye and environment solvent molecule. The probe molecule at higher energy get stable rather than lower energy state with increase in solvent polarity [5,19] as the higher energy state is comparatively polar than the lower energy state. It induced to the lower the energy of transition results red shift. The physico-chemical characteristics of environment are also influenced by the polar group present in the aromatic ring [25-27]. Various investigations have been done on the fluorescence and absorbance spectra of probe molecules in micro environment media. Red shift of indole, its derivative arises due to dipole-dipole interaction between dye and solvent was reported by Mataga et.al. [28,29]. Red shift of a spectrum arises due to interaction of probe-media molecules in lower energy state is less compare to the higher energy state. In this chapter, the spectroscopic behavior of three different dyes safranin O (SO), ANS and thiazolidinediones (TZD) are analyzed in a variety of aprotic and protic medium to investigate the dye-solvent interaction parameters.

2. Materials And Methods

SO, 1,8-ANS and TZD these three dyes of Sigma Aldrich were mixed in water ethanol mixture and collected in crystalline form. Solvents of spectroscopic grade from E. Merck were collected. These solvents are Ethylene glycol (EG), Methyl alcohol (MeOH), ethyl alcohol (EtOH), Double distilled water (30), Dimethyl formamide (DMF), Dioxane (DO), Tetrahydrofuran (THF) and Acetonitrile (ACN)] were purified by fractional distillation. All solutions were prepared triple distilled conductivity water. Emission spectra were measure by using Spectrofluorimeter LS-55 having 2.5 mm slit, made of Perkin Elmer, USA. Absorbance spectra were measure by using UV-VIS spectrophotometer Lamda-35, made of Perkin Elmer. Every spectroscopic measurement was conducted in a constant temperature (298K). Decays analyses were made by using decay analysis software IBHDAS-6.

3. Results And Discussion

Photo physical studies were compared on three different dyes Safranin O, 1,8-ANS and TZD (Fig. 1) having molar extinction coefficient (ϵ) $28448 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, $6300 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ and $22435 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ at 298 K. The absorption maximum for those dyes molecules are appeared at 523 nm, 356 nm and 362 nm respectively.

Fig. 1: three different photosensitive dyes Safranin O, 1,8-ANS and TZD
 The absorption spectral shift occurs to the higher wavelength means bathochromic shift (Fig. 2) with continuous increment of concentration of organic second solvent in aqueous medium in every case.

Fig. 2.: Absorbance of SO, 1,8-ANS and TZD in aqueous solution in presence of Dimethyleformamide[DMF] [DMF]:1: 0M; 2: 1.9045 M; 3: 3.8089 M; 4: 5.7148 M; 5: 7.6187 M; 6: 9.5247 M; 7: 11.430 M; 8: 13.3348 M; 9: 15.9809 M; [SO]: $2.419 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol.dm}^{-3}$ [1,8-ANS]: $0.4667 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol.dm}^{-3}$ [TZD]: $1.5474 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol.dm}^{-3}$

At same time there is increase in intensity of absorbance also for each solvent. The similar behavior is observed for each solvent. Though the intensity of absorption is not equals the intensity of absorption is not equal for different solvents. Variation of interaction among different solvents and dyes cases this difference. Fluorescence intensity for emission spectra so similar increment of intensity with increasing in concentration of second solvent but a reverse shifting of emission wavelength from higher to lower means hypsochromic shift (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3: Fluorescence Intensities of SO, 1,8-ANS and TZD in aqueous solution in presence of Dimethyleformamide[DMF] [DMF]:1: 0 M; 2: 1.9045 M; 3: 3.8089 M; 4: 5.7148 M; 5: 7.6187 M; 6: 9.5247 M; 7: 11.430 M; 8: 13.3348 M; 9: 15.9809 M; [SO]: $2.419 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol.dm}^{-3}$ [1,8-ANS]: $0.4667 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol.dm}^{-3}$ [TZD]: $1.5474 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol.dm}^{-3}$

Developing Langmuir model of absorption to determined the fraction of solid surface of adsorbent adsorbed by liquid adsorbate. In liquid system at equilibrium, there is a competition among adsorbate molecule (Fig. 4) and solvent to adsorb on the surface of adsorbent. The following figure shows clearly the Langmuir model of absorption.

Fig. 4: Langmuir's Model for Competitive Adsorption (Adsorption site is represented by B, a molecules of solvent is represented by S, and adsorbate molecules are represented by shaded oval)

By using solvent adsorption model the absorbance (A) and the fluorescence (F) of dyes in solvents environment it can be said that molecules of organic solvents reside at surface of adsorbent. Using Langmuir model absorption, Lippert equation [17] will be

$$\begin{aligned}
 K &= \frac{n}{n_{\text{Highest}}} = \frac{\text{Number of occupied sites}}{\text{Highest number of available sites}} \\
 &= \text{fraction of engaged sites} \\
 &= \frac{F - F_{\text{Aq}}}{F_{\text{Highest}} - F_{\text{Aq}}} = \frac{A - A_{\text{Aq}}}{A_{\text{Highest}} - A_{\text{Aq}}} \quad \text{(I)}
 \end{aligned}$$

Where, K is the fraction of occupied sites. Absorbance and fluorescence intensity of all these three dyes in aqua solution represented by A_{Aq} and F_{Aq} . Those intensities in present solvents are represented by A and F respectively. Result shows a continuous increment of the emission and absorption intensities is the result of substitution of water by the second solvent on surface of probe molecule. Applying mass action model of equation

Here, M_F , M_A and S_A are the free mass of solvents molecule available, mass of solvents molecule are stick on the probe surface and number of available place on the probe surface.

Concentration of added second medium already occupied and free site are represented by $[A]$ $[F]$, Then total concentration of solvents $[C_T]$ can be represented as

$$[C_T] = [A] + [F] \\ = [F] \quad (\text{Since } [A] \ll [F])$$

$$K = \frac{[M_A]}{[M_F][S_A]} = \frac{[A]}{[F][S_A]} = \frac{[A]}{[C_T][S_A]}$$

Here, K represents equilibrium constant,

Where, $[S_A]$ is the concentration of sites available for adsorption.

Therefore,

$$K[C_T] = \frac{[A]}{[S_A]} = \frac{x}{x_{\max} - x} = \frac{x/x_{\max}}{1 - x/x_{\max}}$$

or,

$$\frac{1}{K[C_T]} = \frac{1-P}{P} = \frac{1}{P} - 1$$

or,

$$\frac{1}{P} = 1 + \frac{1}{K[C_T]} \quad (\text{II}) \quad \text{here, } P = \frac{x}{x_{\max}}$$

Eq. (II) represents the Langmuir adsorption Isotherm. Plot of $1/P$ versus $1/[C]$, using experimental values shows a linear plots (Fig. 5) in every dye solvent interaction. From the positive slope of the line equilibrium constant values were obtained. From analysis the K values order for different solvents are Methyl alcohol (MeOH) < Acetonitrile (CAN) < Ethyl alcohol (EtOH) < Tetrahydrofuran (THF) < Dimethyleformamide (DMF) < Ethyleneglycol (EG) < 1,4-Dioxan (DO)

Fig. 5: Plot of $1/Y$ Vs $1/[D.O.]$

These difference of K values (Table 1) does not follow dialectic constant, indicates specific type of interaction among solute solvent rather than universal interaction. The clustered water molecule surrounding to the solute molecule is replaced by added second solvent indicate there may be an interaction of water molecules with second solvent also. The Stokes shift ($\Delta\nu$) data (Table 1) shows there is an interaction of hydrated dye molecules and molecules of second solvent form an excited complex. This shift occurs due to energy of interaction between water and second solvent. The Stokes shift values are near about the reverse order of equilibrium constant values.

Table 1: K and $\Delta\nu$ Values of dyes in different second Solvents at 298 K.

2 nd Solvent	Dielectric Constant(D)	Dye	K_{abs} /dm ³ mol ⁻¹	K_{emi} /dm ³ mol ⁻¹	K_{av} /dm ³ mol ⁻¹	Diff. in Stokes shift $\overline{\Delta\nu}$ (cm ⁻¹)
ACN	37.4	ST	1.45	1.34	1.40	795
EtOH	24.6		1.67	1.80	1.74	750
DMF	36.7		1.92	2.02	1.97	598
EG	40.7		2.12	2.18	2.15	548
DO	2.2		2.21	2.20	2.21	161
MeOH	32.70		1.34	1.44	1.39	543
THF	7.58		1.79	1.75	1.77	720
ACN	37.4	1,8-ANS	9.18	7.02	8.10	3377
EtOH	24.6		2.57	3.63	3.10	3053
DMF	36.7		14.69	17.18	15.94	4107
EG	40.7		1.93	3.00	2.47	2806
DO	2.2		18.84	9.89	14.37	3694
MeOH	32.70		8.72	12.51	10.62	3998
THF	7.58		2.72	3.00	2.86	2877
ACN	37.4	TZD	1.26	1.42	1.34	699
EtOH	24.6		1.52	1.92	1.72	657
DMF	36.7		1.71	2.16	1.94	612
EG	40.7		2.50	2.18	2.34	575
DO	2.2		2.30	2.45	2.38	534
MeOH	32.70		1.68	1.46	1.57	489
THF	7.58		1.62	1.51	1.57	672

3.1. Stokes shift:

The solvent interaction in the lower energy state and higher energy state for these three dyes resulted as spectral shift of fluorescence and absorbance. This fluorescence and absorbance shift occurs within the range of wavelength 566 nm to 582 nm and 521 nm to 535 nm respectively for Safranin O, 563 nm to 356 nm and 501 nm to 540 nm respectively for 1,8-ANS, 360 nm to 372 nm and 510 nm to 536 nm respectively for TZD. Stokes shift may be an important parameter as evidence for explanation of probe-medium interaction. Hyperbolic curve obtained from the plot of Stokes shift as a function of increasing second solvent concentration are shown in Fig. 6. The competition of second solvent with the water clustered solute molecule also supported by the adsorption model.

Fig. 6: Plot of Stokes ($\overline{\Delta\nu}$) shift with [2nd Solvent]

The repulsion among second solvent and probe molecule may cause this hyperbolic curve. Solvent dependent stoke shift of dye with respect to the dipole moment and dielectric constant

of solvent was investigated by Lippert-Mataga [30-33] equation

$$\bar{\nu}_A - \bar{\nu}_B = \frac{2}{hc} \left(\frac{\epsilon - 1}{2\epsilon + 1} - \frac{n^2 - 1}{2n^2 + 1} \right) \frac{(\mu_E - \mu_G)}{a^3} + Const \quad (III)$$

Here, wave number of absorbance and fluorescence are represented by $\bar{\nu}_A$ and $\bar{\nu}_F$ respectively. Also h , c , ϵ , n and a represent Plank constant, velocity of light in vacuum, dielectric constant, refraction index [34-37] and radius of the cavity to occupy fluorophore. Dipole moment in the higher energy state and lower energy state are represented by μ_E and μ_G respectively. By using Lippert-Mataga equation we can plot Stokes shift and E_T^{30} (solvent parameter) shows a distinct separation for protic (Ethyl alcohol, Methyl alcohol, Water and Ethylene glycol) and aprotic (Dioxane, tetrahydrofuran, Dimethylformamide and Acetonitrile) solvent (Fig. 7). This is also a support specific type of interaction of dye solvent. This may be due to hydrogen bonding with protic solvent. The solvent polarity indicators scale like E_T^{30} is more applicable in case of charge transfer molecule. The plot of Stokes shift with E_T^{30} [38-40] shows a high slope for protic solvent than aprotic solvent indicating different interaction of dyes with protic and aprotic solvent.

Fig. 7: Plot of E_T^{30} parameter vs. $\Delta \bar{\nu}$ for three dyes.

3.2. Life time measurement:

Local environment of dye in solvent, fluorescence can be studied by lifetime as it plays an important role of indicator. The lifetime (τ) and quantum (Φ_f) yield in various solvents are given in table 2. The values of radiative (k_r) and non-radiative (k_{nr}) rate constants are obtained from the $k_r = \Phi_f/\tau$ and $1/\tau = k_r + k_{nr}$ relation, also given in table 2.

Table 2: E_T^{30} and life time values of probes in various solvents

Solvent	Dye	E_T^{30}	Φ_f	Life time (τ) X 10 ⁻⁹	$k_r \times 10^{-9}/s^{-1}$	$k_{nr} \times 10^{-9}/s^{-1}$
WATER		63.1	0.12	0.23804	0.37	3.11
ACN	SO	46.0	0.43	3.56569	0.49	0.42
	EtOH	51.9	0.45	4.14652	0.25	0.26
	DMF	43.9	0.53	1.97691	0.38	0.46
	EG	56.3	0.56	2.30233	0.26	0.33
	DO	36.3	0.33	6.23803	0.49	0.34
	MeOH	55.5	0.46	2.61032	0.22	0.33
	THF	37.4	0.43	6.62809	0.21	0.28
WATER		63.1	0.08	0.25802	0.27	3.30

		46.0	0.46	3.55585	0.19	0.22
ACN						
EtOH	1,8-ANS	51.9	0.40	4.21076	0.15	0.23
DMF		43.9	0.33	1.88734	0.08	0.16
EG		56.3	0.52	2.44326	0.16	0.13
DO		36.3	0.63	6.29809	0.09	0.04
MeOH		55.5	0.66	2.5978	0.10	0.05
THF		37.4	0.50	6.54367	0.08	0.08
WATER		63.1	0.12	0.34092	0.38	0.79
ACN		46.0	0.34	3.22465	0.22	0.43
EtOH		51.9	0.32	4.35674	0.23	0.23
DMF	TZD	43.9	0.34	1.77665	0.21	0.20
EG		56.3	0.54	2.3243	0.19	0.21
DO		36.3	0.56	6.28652	0.12	0.08
MeOH		55.5	0.32	2.44563	0.21	0.13
THF		37.4	0.44	6.32456	0.23	0.16

Plot of $\log(k_{nr}/k_r)$ of salute with respect to $E_T(30)$ of solvent shows two set of relation (Fig. 8) for all three dyes solvents interaction indicating specific interaction.

Fig. 8: Plot of $E_T(30)$ parameter vs $\log(k_{nr}/k_r)$ in different second solvents for three dyes

4. Conclusions

- 1) Every dyes interacted with second solvent in aqueous are not uniform in nature in case of all these three dyes in different solvents indicate specific type of interaction.
- 2) Different interaction parameter values of dye molecule with neighbor solvent environment shows a hyperbolic curve with increase in concentration of second solvent with different slope values signify Specific interaction.
- 3) Stokes shift vs $E_T(30)$ plot shows two separate set of linearity in protic and aprotic solvents also support specific type of interaction.
- 4) $\log(k_{nr}/k_r)$ vs $E_T(30)$ plot of these dyes also shows separation among protic and aprotic solvents also indicate the way of specific type of interaction.

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